

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

Year 1

Year 2

Year 3

Year 4

Year 5

WP3 – Milestone 3

Daniel Figueiredo (UU) & Nicoleta Suciú (UCSC)

Milestone number: 3

Milestone title: Model data requirements identified.

Lead beneficiary: IISPV

Due date: 31-12-2020

Publishing date: 18-12-2020

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Title	Sustainable Plant Protection Transition; A global health approach
Project Acronym	SPRINT
Call Identifier	H2020-SFS-2019-2; Sustainable Food Security
Grant Agreement no.	862568
Starting Date	01-09-2020
End Date	31-08-2025
Project duration	60 months
Website address	www.sprint-h2020.eu
Overall Project coordinator	Prof. Dr. V. GEISSEN (violette.geissen@wur.nl)
Scientific coordinator	Assoc. Prof. Dr. P.T.J. SCHEEPERS (paul.scheepers@radboudumc.nl)
EU project officer	Alessandro CHIODINI

REPORT INFORMATION

Report Title	Model data requirements identified.
Milestone Number	M3
Milestone Title	Model data requirements identified.
Means of verification	List of required existing models and required input data.
Related Work Package	WP3
Author(s) of report (institution)	UU, UCSC, IISPV, RU
Principle Author e-mail	d.m.figueiredo@uu.nl / nicoleta.suciu@unicatt.it
Editor(s)	IISPV
E--Mail(s)	montserrat.marques@urv.cat / neus.gonzalez@fundacio.urv.cat
Milestone Due Date	31-12-2020
Milestone publish date	18-12-2020

Table of contents

1. From agricultural spraying to human exposure	4
1.1 Fate of pesticides in the environment.....	4
1.2 Exposure of the population	4
1.2.1 Environmental exposure	4
1.2.2 Occupational exposure	5
1.2.3 Dietary exposure (i.e. via food intake).....	5
2. Modelling the fate of pesticides	5
2.1 Fate of pesticides.....	5
2.1.1 Drift, Volatilization & Dispersion – BROWSE model	5
2.1.2 Runoff – PRZM Model	6
2.1.3 Wind erosion – New Model	6
2.1.4 Water and sediments – TOXSWA Model	6
3. Modelling human exposure to pesticides	7
3.1 Inhalation and dermal exposures	7
3.2 Dermal contact.....	7
3.3 Dust ingestion	7
3.4 Dietary exposure	7
4. Modelling Ecosystem, Plant and Animal exposure to pesticides	8
4.1 Ecosystem and Plants.....	8
4.2 Animals.....	8
5. Data input	8
5.1 For fate modelling	8
5.2 For exposure modelling.....	10
6. Connections between models	10
7. Concluding remark	10
References	10

1. From agricultural spraying to human exposure

The purpose of this chapter is to explain the human exposure to an applied pesticide, by describing the physical and chemical processes involved. The view presented here gives a broader explanation on the processes. A more detailed explanation on each of the processes can be found in literature.

1.1 Fate of pesticides in the environment

This sub-chapter gives a general overview of the possible fate of pesticides once these are sprayed in agricultural fields.

From application to environmental compartments

1. Application occurs during a short period, where the boom sprayer moves at a given speed and distributes the compound(s), which is/are in a tank mixture.
2. While application occurs, droplets can either evaporate, can drift* and remain airborne (greatly dependent on droplet size and settling velocity), can go on the target area, or can drift and deposit in off-target area. These movements are mainly induced via advection due to wind stress.
3. A fraction of the deposited ingredient can evaporate from both the target and off-target areas, greatly depending on its vapour pressure, this is, the capacity to volatile. The substance that is volatized then flows downwind.
4. A fraction of the substance that is applied can become bound to soil and due to wind erosion transported in particle-bound form.
5. Pesticides run-off to nearby water surfaces can happen if rain events occur.
6. The gas-phase and the particle-phase of the substance can then travel towards the residences, infiltrate to the indoor environment and accumulate over time. Accumulation is highly dependent on each pesticide half-life, as well as indoor circulation and resuspension.

In sum, the abovementioned steps explain the existence of pesticides in 4 main environmental compartments, which are:

Soil / Air / Water / Dust

**Drift - The definition of drift is when liquids are forced under pressure through small orifices (like sprayer nozzles) and are sheared into small aerosols or particles. Owing to gravitational forces and the viscosity of air, the rate of fall to ground can be predicted by Stokes Law and is proportional to the radius of the particles (Felsot et al. 2010).*

1.2 Exposure of the population

The total exposure of an individual to pesticides is the sum of the 3 main exposures:

Environmental, Occupational (if applicable) and **Dietary**.

1.2.1 Environmental exposure

Environmental exposure can occur via 4 different routes (see underlined), which are:

- Inhalation and Dermal exposure from the total airborne fraction;

- Dermal contact to contaminated surfaces (e.g. indoor dust);
- Dust Ingestion

1.2.2 Occupational exposure

Farmers have this additional exposure due to their work (e.g. spraying or managing land). To assess the degree of exposure (e.g. low, medium, high), questions will be asked regarding their activities, use of protective equipment and other relevant factors for occupational exposure assessment.

1.2.3 Dietary exposure (i.e. via food intake)

Besides environmental exposure, all population is exposed to pesticides via food intake. The degree of exposure via this route is highly dependent on each individual's diet and the origin of the consumed products.

2. Modelling the fate of pesticides

2.1 Fate of pesticides

2.1.1 Drift, Volatilization & Dispersion – BROWSE model

The BROWSE model will be used to calculate airborne pesticide concentrations from drift and volatilization. This model comprises a drift module, based on the Silsoe Spray Drift Model and a volatilization & dispersion module based on the couple PEARL-OPS. Each model within BROWSE is briefly introduced below:

SILSOE – Model for Drift

"The Silsoe Spray Drift Model (Butler Ellis & Miller, 2010) is a particle tracking model, which simulates the release of droplets from a moving boom and calculates their trajectory, subject to complex air flows close to the nozzle, and then assumes a random walk further away." (Cited from [Browse 2013](#) report).

PEARL - Model for Volatilization

Pearl (Pesticide Emission Assessment at Regional and Local Scales) is a one-dimensional numerical model of pesticide behaviour in the soil-plant system, which has been developed in close co-operation with two Dutch institutes (Alterra and RIVM). Pesticide volatilization refers to evaporation or sublimation of a volatile compound. Using this model, volatilization from soil and plants can be estimated from input of the physic-chemical properties of the pesticide and the prevailing meteorological conditions. Pearl gives the emission rate from soil and plants for a given pesticide ([Van den Berg et al. 2016](#)).

OPS - Model for Dispersion and Deposition

For dispersion and deposition, the model is OPS-St (Short term Operational Priority Substances). OPS-St is a version of OPS for shorter range (~ 0 - 50 km). The OPS-St model is used on an hourly basis and computes hourly concentrations and depositions for a limited area. It is used for modelling of dispersion and deposition of pollutants for the Netherlands on both local and national scale. The model can be described as a Lagrangian

(trajectory) model which acts as a Gaussian plume model for local situations ([Sauter et al. 2016](#)).

2.1.2 Runoff – PRZM Model

The PRZM (Pesticide Root Zone Model) model will be used for Runoff. This is a one-dimensional non-deterministic compartmental model for the prediction of chemical movement in unsaturated soils by vertical chromatographic leaching. PRZM is based on a one-dimensional finite-difference code. The model consists of hydrologic (flow) and chemical transport components to simulate runoff, erosion, plant uptake, leaching, decay, foliar washoff, and volatilisation. Pesticide transport and fate processes include advection, dispersion, molecular diffusion, and soil sorption. The model includes soil temperature effects, volatilisation and vapour phase transport in soils, irrigation simulation and a method of characteristics algorithm to eliminate numerical dispersion. Predictions can be made for daily, monthly or annual output. PRZM allows the user to perform dynamic simulations considering pulse loads, predicting peak events, and estimating time-varying emission or concentration profiles in layered soils.

2.1.3 Wind erosion – New Model

For wind erosion, a model [to be named] will be developed in R software based on input from the literature review by [Jarrah et al. 2020](#). It will consist mainly in the mathematical formulations used for agricultural settings.

2.1.4 Water and sediments – TOXSWA Model

The TOXSWA (acronym of TOXic substances in Surface Waters) will be used in SPRINT. It is a quasi-two-dimensional numerical model of pesticide behaviour in a small surface water system, incl. its sediment. Indeed, TOXSWA describes the behaviour of pesticides in a water body at the edge-of-field scale, i.e. a ditch, pond or stream adjacent to a single field. It calculates pesticide concentrations in the water layer in horizontal direction only and in the sediment layer in both horizontal and vertical directions. TOXSWA considers four processes: (i) transport, (ii) transformation, (iii) sorption and (iv) volatilisation. In the water layer, pesticides are transported by advection and dispersion, while in the sediment, diffusion is included as well. The transformation rate covers the combined effects of hydrolysis, photolysis and biodegradation and it is a function of temperature. It does not simulate formation of metabolites. Sorption to suspended solids and to sediment is described by the Freundlich equation. Sorption to macrophytes is described by a linear sorption isotherm. Pesticides are transported across the water-sediment interface by diffusion and by advection (upward or downward seepage; Fig. 1)

In order to simulate the flow dynamics in an edge-of-field water body in a realistic way, the field-scale system is defined as the downstream part of a small catchment basin. Water

flow is described with the aid of a simple water balance, accounting for all major incoming and outgoing water fluxes. The water level is a function of time, but assumed to be constant in the water body system considered. Water levels are calculated either by assuming uniform flow conditions (Chézy-Manning equation), or by assuming a backwater curve in front of a weir. TOXSWA uses an explicit finite-difference scheme to solve the water balance and mass conservation equations. Distances between the nodes in the water and sediment layers are in the order of magnitude of metres and millimetres, respectively.

3. Modelling human exposure to pesticides

Part of the OBO modelling framework, the exposure module, will be used to calculate exposure of the participants in each case study site. The OBO exposure module was initially developed in MATLAB, but it has now been transferred to R software. The following sub-chapters explain the contents of this module.

3.1 Inhalation and dermal exposures

For inhalation and dermal pathways, the framework uses the mathematical formulation explained in [Zhao et al. 2014](#), since this approach is reliable and is commonly found in literature. For inhalation rate, we use tabulated values from the EPA ([U.S. EPA, 2011](#)).

For dermal exposure we use [Schlich et al. 2010](#) formulation to calculate skin surface area in case the weight and height are known. If not, tabulated values from the EPA Exposure Factors Handbook are used. We use [Shanshan Shi & Bin Zhao \(2013\)](#) to account for seasonal variation for deposition velocity onto human body surfaces. We do not consider a clothing barrier ([Morrison et al. 2016](#)).

3.2 Dermal contact

To assess exposure via dermal contact, we use the formulation presented in [Zheng et al. 2017](#). Here, we include contact with contaminated surfaces but do not include direct contact with liquid formulation.

3.3 Dust ingestion

For ingestion, the formulation used is also presented in [Zheng et al. 2017](#).

Different recommended values for dust ingestion rate can be found in literature, however some are more conservative (e.g. [MOE, 2011](#)) than others (e.g. [Wilson et al. 2016](#)).

We use the values proposed by [Wilson et al. 2016](#), since it is one of the more recent studies in this field and because it uses a hand-to-mouth model (one of the main drivers for incidental ingestion) to predict dust ingestion rates, while accounting for age group and for the type of surface (hard, soft or mix).

3.4 Dietary exposure

Dietary exposure is not included in the OBO exposure module yet. For dietary exposure, different models are available in literature, such as the MCRA 8 software developed in the

ACROPOLIS project, which includes various options for probabilistic modelling as described in [van der Voet et al. \(2014\)](#) for single-compound and cumulative dietary exposure. Another example is the cumulative dietary (SHEDS-Dietary) used in the US SHEDS multimedia model ([Zartarian et al. 2008](#)). However, both these tools are more used in risk assessment for aggregate and cumulative modelling.

Our approach will be to calculate the dietary exposure based on the self-reported dietary habits of the studied population combined with the average concentration of pesticide (active ingredient) in food (mainly fruits and vegetables) according to the available pesticide residue databases.

4. Modelling Ecosystem, Plant and Animal exposure to pesticides

4.1 Ecosystem and Plants

According to the SPRINT proposal, "*Bioaccumulation in crops (P) and non-target species (E) will be calculated using improved existing fate models, existing datasets (task 3.1)*"

The fate models described in section 2 will be used. However, the improvement will depend on the output of the literature review done by task 3.1.

4.2 Animals

At this stage of the project, we do not know which animals can be studied in each case study site. Given the current knowledge, we are aiming to assess exposure in three different animals: dairy cows, chicken and fish. A literature review needs to be performed to search available models to be integrated in the OBO exposure module. There are some models showing promises such as those in <https://merlin-expo.eu/> (e.g. fish and cow model).

In addition, consultation with different experts within SPRINT will be carried out after the literature review is performed.

5. Data input

In the following 2 sections (5.1 Fate modelling and 5.2 Exposure modelling) a list of all inputs required to run the aforementioned modelling steps is presented. The variables here described are only those that need to be collected or measured in each case study. Additional data will be collected from literature and this solely pertains to the physico-chemical properties of each pesticide.

5.1 For fate modelling

List of inputs needed for fate modelling calculation, divided considering the environmental matrices:

Longitude & Latitude

Climate data (weather station close to field; max 5 km)

- ✓ Air Temperature (hourly, daily)

- ✓ Rainfall (hourly, daily)
- ✓ Wind speed (hourly, daily)
- ✓ Wind angle
- ✓ Wind erosion potential
- ✓ ET actual (daily)
- ✓ Solar radiation (daily)
- ✓ Saltation
- ✓ Erosion, total and PM10
- ✓ Maximum particles transport

Soil

- ✓ Texture
- ✓ Organic matter content
- ✓ Hydraulic properties
- ✓ Slope
- ✓ Field area (ha)

Crop

- ✓ BBCH (i.e. Scale used to identify the growth stage of plants)
- ✓ Leaf area
- ✓ Crop Height (just for fruits)

Water body

- ✓ Size
- ✓ Depth
- ✓ Water flow (no mandatory)
- ✓ Distance from field

Agronomic management

- ✓ Planting time
- ✓ Harvesting time
- ✓ Type of irrigation
- ✓ Pesticide application
 - Product dose
 - Conc. a.i. in product
 - Applied spray volume
 - Neublizer type
 - Spray direction (downward/upward)
 - Sprayer type
 - Drift reduction %
 - Application type
 - Forward speed

5.2 For exposure modelling

List of inputs needed for human exposure calculations:

- Average time spent indoors – household (Hours)
- Body weight (kg)
- Sex (M or F)
- Height (cm)
- Concentration of gas and particle-phase pesticides in outdoor air at participants household.
- Concentration of pesticides in indoor dust
- PM10 Concentration (or total suspended particulate matter)
- Season (Winter, Summer, Transitional)

6. Connections between models

Connections between the different models and possible adaptations will be reported in milestone 4 (due month 14). Here, the flow chart of models will be presented, including input and output relationships.

7. Concluding remark

We presented here the models and input data required to perform simulations at the local scale of fate of pesticides and exposure of ecosystem, plants, animals and health. It is important to stress that this is not designed specifically for the case study sites in SPRINT given that at this moment we still do not have all information from the types of cultivation, spraying techniques and so on. We selected these models because they allow us to cover all processes and give some flexibility to adapt for different scenarios (e.g. downwind vs upwind spraying).

References

Felsot, Allan S. , Unsworth, John B. , Linders, Jan B. H. J. , Roberts, Graham , Rautman, Dirk , Harris, Caroline and Carazo, Elizabeth(2010) 'Agrochemical spray drift; assessment and mitigation—A review*', *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part B*, 45: 8, 889 – 911, First published on: 27 October 2010 (iFirst). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03601234.2010.515161>

Jarrah, M., Mayel, S., Tatarko, J., Funk, R., & Kuka, K. (2020). A review of wind erosion models: Data requirements, processes, and validity. *Catena*, 187(March 2019), 104388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2019.104388>

MOE (2011) Ontario Ministry of the Environment (MOE): Rationale for the Development of Soil and Groundwater Standards for Use at Contaminated Sites in Ontario (2011).

Morrison GC, Weschler CJ, Bekö G, Koch HM, Salthammer T, Schripp T, et al. 2016. Role of clothing in both accelerating and impeding dermal absorption of airborne SVOCs. *JESEE* 26(1): 113-118.

Ross Wilson, Ian Mitchell & G. Mark Richardson (2016) Estimation of dust ingestion rates in units of surface area per day using a mechanistic hand-to-mouth model, *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 22:4, 874-881, DOI: 10.1080/10807039.2015.1115956.

Sauter, F., van Zanten, M., Swaluw, E. Van Der, Aben, J., Leeuw, F. De, & Jaarsveld, H. Van. (2016). The OPS-model. Description of OPS 4.5.0, 2016-05-12.

Schlich, E; Schumm, M; Schlich, M (2010). "3-D-Body-Scan als anthropometrisches Verfahren zur Bestimmung der spezifischen Körperoberfläche". *Ernährungs Umschau*. 57: 178-183.

Shanshan Shi & Bin Zhao (2013): DOI: 10.1080/02786826.2013.843772.

U.S. EPA. (2011) Exposure Factors Handbook 2011 Edition (Final Report). U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, DC, EPA/600/R-09/052F, 2011.

Van den Berg, F., Tiktak, A., Boesten, J. J. T. I., & van der Linden, A. M. A. (2016). PEARL model for pesticide behaviour and emissions in soil-plant system: description of processes. Wageningen UR, 61(February), 134.

van der Voet, H., de Boer, W.J., Kruisselbrink, J.W., Goedhart, P.W., van der Heijden, G.W.A.M., Kennedy, M.C., et al. 2014. The MCRA model for probabilistic single compound and cumulative risk assessment of pesticides. *Food Chem. Toxicol.*

Zartarian, V.G., Glen, G., Smith, L., Xue, J., 2008. Stochastic Human Exposure and Dose Simulation Model for Multimedia, Multipathway Chemicals SHEDS-Multimedia Model Version 3 Technical Manual. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, EPA/600/R-08/118.

Zhao, B. & Shi, S. (2014). Modeled Exposure Assessment via Inhalation and Dermal Pathways to Airborne Semivolatile Organic Compounds (SVOCs) in Residences. Article in *Environmental Science & Technology* - April 2014. <http://doi.org/10.1021/es500235q>.

Zheng, X., Qiao, L., Covaci, A., Sun, R., Guo, H., & Zheng, J. (2017). Chemosphere Brominated and phosphate flame retardants (FRs) in indoor dust from different microenvironments: Implications for human exposure via dust ingestion and dermal contact. *Chemosphere*, 184, 185-191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.05.167>